

WüSpace Paper Format

December 10, 2023

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Abstract

This document outlines the writing guidelines and layout requirements established by WüSpace e. V., a non-profit student aerospace association. WüSpace publishes various materials, including (working) papers, on its Zenodo community. These guidelines ensure a consistent and professional style.

1 Introduction

WüSpace e. V. is a student association dedicated to contributing to the scientific community. Financial constraints make it difficult to publish valuable research outcomes that cannot be published into big journals. To solve this, WüSpace publishes various documents, including (working) papers, on its Zenodo community¹.

WüSpace provides templates and specifications outlining the required publishing styles to maintain a consistent style for these papers. This document, which adheres to the specified style, outlines the writing guidelines and layout requirements mentioned above.

2 Writing Style

2.1 Language

The language used is English. German publications may be exceptionally published, but must be marked accordingly.

Use gender-neutral, inclusive language wherever appropriate.

2.2 Citation

Citation is a fundamental practice in scholarly literature, enabling the acknowledgment and referencing of sources and context in one's research. Citations show how one's argument is connected to other academic works that support or challenge it.

2.2.1 Citation Style

We use a citation style based on the IEEE style² described in [1].

The following style rules should be observed:

1. Direct quotes are enclosed in quotation marks.

¹ Available online at <https://zenodo.org/communities/wuespace>.

² We chose the IEEE style because it is popular in technical fields and computer science.

Specification

Internally approved

License

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2. Each citation, whether direct or indirect, must be accompanied by a source reference.
3. All cited sources must be listed in the bibliography with a continuous numerical digit surrounded by square brackets, e.g., “[1]”.
4. Source references consist of the literature-designating digit surrounded by square brackets (e.g., “[1]”).
5. Specific references are provided after a comma, e.g., “[1, Fig. 1.3]”.
6. Page numbers are indicated with the prefix “p.” after the comma, e.g., “[1, p. 5]”.
7. When citing multiple pages, use the prefix “pp.” and describe the page range as follows: “[1, pp. 45–46]”.
8. Always use page ranges, never “f.” or “ff.”.
9. If a direct quote ends with a period (.), it is placed after the source reference: “A direct quote” [1, p. 35].
10. If a direct quote ends with a punctuation mark other than a period, it is included within the quote: “A question?” [1, p. 35].
11. The source reference is part of the sentence that surrounds it and should be mentioned before the sentence ends.
12. The source reference can also be directly integrated into the text. In this case, the form “Authors [Digit]” should be used. Typically, the last names of the authors are used. If a source has more than two authors, the main author followed by the abbreviation “et al.” should be used, such as Cornelsen et al. [1].

Several examples are shown in Listing 1.

2.2.2 Block Quotes

Block quotes may be used for citations exceeding 40 words. They have an indentation and are written without quotation marks. The following applies:

1. Direct quotes with a minimum length of 40 words can be cited in the form of a block quote.
2. Block quotes do not use quotation marks.
3. Block quotes are identified by an indentation at the left margin.
4. Source references are placed on the line below the block quote, right-aligned after an em dash (—), in the form described for directly incorporated source references (as if they were embedded in the text).

An example is shown in Listing 2.

```
"Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua" @test[p. 45].
```

```
Another question then becomes "Dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua?" @test[pp. 45-57].
```

```
Here something is paraphrased, which can be found in the source @test2.
```

```
Mentioning multiple sources is also possible @test@test2.
```

```
As described by #cite(<test>, form: "prose", supplement: "p. 15"), the source can also be directly incorporated into the text.
```

```
"Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua" [2, p. 45].
```

```
Another question then becomes "Dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua?" [2, pp. 45-57].
```

```
Here something is paraphrased, which can be found in the source [3].
```

```
Mentioning multiple sources is also possible [2], [3].
```

```
As described by Example-Author [2, p. 15], the source can also be directly incorporated into the text.
```

Listing 1: Citation Examples (for some reason, the short question in the second example spans over ten pages 😊)

```
#lorem(20)
```

```
#quote(block: true, attribution: <test>[
```

```
  #lorem(40)
```

```
]
```

```
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magnam aliquam quaerat.
```

```
  Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magnam aliquam quaerat voluptatem. Ut enim aequae doleamus animo, cum corpore dolemus, fieri tamen permagna accessio potest, si aliquod aeternum et infinitum impendere.
```

```
    — Example-Author [2]
```

Listing 2: Block Quote Example in Typst

3 Layout

The layout is inspired by the LaPreprint template [4], but designed from scratch to perfectly fit our requirements.

3.1 Units

The two units the sizes get measured in are Points (pt) and Millimeters (mm). For the conversion, we follow Typst's conversion factor [5]:

$$1 \text{ mm} = 2.83465 \text{ pt}$$

$$1 \text{ pt} = \frac{1}{2.83465} \text{ mm}$$

As the base font size (rem), we use 11 pt (rem := 11 pt). Many sizes are defined by a product of rem with 1.2^x . For convenience, we introduce the following notation:

$$s_x := 1.2^x \text{ rem}$$

To get a sense of what that means, let's look at a few examples:

$$s_{-1} = 1.2^{-1} \text{ rem} = \frac{1}{1.2} \text{ rem} \approx 9.167 \text{ pt}$$

$$s_0 = 1.2^0 \text{ rem} = 1 \text{ rem} \approx 11 \text{ pt}$$

$$s_1 = 1.2^1 \text{ rem} = 1.2 \text{ rem} \approx 13.2 \text{ pt}$$

$$s_2 = 1.2^2 \text{ rem} = 1.44 \text{ rem} \approx 15.84 \text{ pt}$$

3.2 Pages

3.2.1 Page size

The pages are portrait DIN A4 pages with a width of 210 mm and a height of 297 mm.

3.2.2 Page elements

All pages contain a header, the main content area, and a footer.

You can find a visualization of the layout (also including the additional elements of title pages described in Section 3.2.3) in Figure 1.

The main content area has the following margins:

- To the left** 60 mm
- To the right** 20 mm
- To the top and bottom** 30 mm

The header and footer are repeated across all pages. They have the same horizontal margins as the main content area. They have a vertical margin from the main content area of s_4 .

The header contains, aligned to the bottom-left, with a text opacity of 50%, to the left the text "DOI: ", followed by the document's DOI (as a link) in the format 10.XXXX/YYYYYYY. In the same line, aligned to the right, the text "License: CC-BY 4.0", followed by the CC-BY 4.0 badge in Figure 2 with a height of s_0 .

Figure 1: Page elements (including title page elements)

Figure 2: CC-BY 4.0 Badge.
Source: <https://creativecommons.org/mission/downloads/>, used in accordance with <https://creativecommons.org/policies/>.
Not covered by the CC-BY 4.0 License.

The footer contains, aligned to the top-center, the page number in the format “X / Y”, where X is the current page number and Y is the final page number.

3.2.3 Title Page Elements

The title page contains additional elements:

Logo The WüSpace e. V. logo. With a width of 30 mm, it sits with a margin of 20 mm to the left as well as 35 mm to the top (slightly below the beginning of the content area and with a 10 mm gap to the content area).

Margin Notes Aligned to the left with a side margin of 20 mm to the left and 5 mm to the main content area on the right, the margin notes are aligned to the bottom of the main content area. It contains various information under unnumbered level 2 headings. The different sections have a vertical gap of s_6 .

3.2.4 Landscape pages

For big horizontal figures (tables, etc.), you can use landscape pages. They use the same vertical margins of 30 mm for their main content area (and have header and footer above and below that, respectively). Horizontally, they have a margin of 20 mm on both sides.

If you want to use multiple columns, use a gutter of 5 mm. An example can be seen with Listing 1 and Listing 2.

3.3 Text

The Roboto font family is used for all text within the paper.

3.3.1 Base Size

The text has a size of $s_0 = 11$ pt. The lines have a leading of s_{-2} . The paragraph spacing is s_1 .³

3.3.2 Headings

Headings are displayed with a font weight of 700 (“Bold”). They are prefixed by a numbering that follows the format X.Y.Z [...], where the numbers are arabic numerals (1, 2, 3, ...).

The sizes of headings are based on their heading level. Headings of level 4 and above are discouraged. They are displayed in an italic bold style.

Heading Level	Font Size	Space above	Space below
1	s_2	s_4	s_{-2}
2	s_1	s_2	s_{-2}
≥ 3	s_0	s_2	s_{-2}

Table 1: Heading Formatting

³This matches a line spacing value of 1.2 and a paragraph spacing value of 5.55 pt in Microsoft Office Word.

3.3.3 Links

Links have the color #45297 and are underlined. No additional styling is applied to images that are links.

3.3.4 Footnotes

Footnotes are indicated using plain arabic numerals (1, 2, 3, ...) in superscript. The numbering sequence persists throughout the entire document and is not reset per page.

When a page includes footnotes, the main content area is shortened to accommodate the footnote area at the bottom. This area has a margin of s_0 from the rest of the text. Beneath this margin, a 0.5 pt line in #452897 with a length of 30 mm is positioned along the left edge of the main content area, signaling the presence of footnotes. Below this line, the footnotes are displayed with a gap of s_{-1} between each. The footnote text is presented in a font size of s_{-1} .

For instance, consider this footnote⁴ containing some example text. Another footnote⁵ is provided to illustrate the gap.

3.4 Title Section

The title section, marking the main content area of the first page, is structured as follows:

1. A horizontal line, colored in #452897 with a stroke width of 0.5 pt.
2. A vertical space of s_0 .
3. The paper title, detailed in Section 3.4.1.
4. Another vertical space of s_0 .
5. The publication date, outlined in Section 3.4.2.
6. A paragraph break.
7. The authors and affiliations, explained in Section 3.4.3.
8. The abstract, clarified in Section 3.4.4.
9. A vertical space of s_0 .
10. A horizontal line, colored in #452897 with a stroke width of 0.5 pt.
11. A vertical space of s_6 to separate the content.

3.4.1 Title

The paper's title is presented with a font size of $s_{2.5}$ and a bold font weight of 700.

3.4.2 Publication Date

The publication date gets displayed as normal text using the format "[Month Name] [DD], [YYYY]" – for example, "November 23, 2023".

⁴ Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua quaerat.

⁵ Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua quaerat voluptatem. Ut enim aequale doleamus.

Figure 3: ORCID iD Icon.

Source: https://orcid.figshare.com/articles/figure/ORCID_iD_icon_graphics/5008697 licensed as CC0

3.4.3 Authors & Affiliations

To start, the first line introduces all authors - denoted as **X**, **Y**, and **Z**.

Following that, affiliations are detailed, each associated with a specific symbol (*, †, ‡, §, ¶, ||, **, ††, and so on). These symbols are utilized for numbering and are explained in the next line. After each author's name, their corresponding affiliations are indicated in superscript, using the assigned symbols in a comma-separated format.

In cases where an author possesses an ORCID iD, a corresponding icon (Figure 3), linked to their profile, is displayed after the affiliation symbols. This icon maintains a height of s_{-2} to prevent any impact on the line height.

A complete example is illustrated as follows:

Severus Snape*, **Dolores Umbridge*†** , and **Tom Riddle**

* Hogwarts School of Witchcraft and Wizardry, † Ministry of Magic

3.4.4 Abstract

The abstract is presented beneath an unnumbered heading with a font size of $s_{1.5}$. This heading, while unnumbered and sized differently, is formatted consistently with a level 1 heading in terms of spacing.

3.5 Figures, Listings & Tables

The positioning of elements such as figures, listings, and tables is at the authors' discretion, but should be chosen with readability in mind. Every figure, listing, and table should have a caption, including its identifier (its type and a continuous number) with which it can be referenced.

While small illustrations can be placed in the left margin, the most common positioning is in the main content area, like Figure 4.

Figure 4: Example image
Source: Ebenezer42 from Pixabay

Logo
(Title Page)

Margin Notes
(Title Page)

Main Content Area

Header

Main Content Area

Footer

Bibliography

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